

Structure of Education System of India and U.S.A at Secondary Level: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

Education is the base of human life. Education is never ending process of human growth and development and its period stretches from cradle to grave. Education, in real sense, is to humanize humanity and to make life progressive, cultured and civilized. It is very important for the progress of individual and society. Through education, man develops his thinking and reasoning problem solving and creativity & intelligence, aptitude, positive sentiments, skill, good value & attitudes

Keywords

Education System, Comparative Study, USA.

Introduction

The educational system of India, U.S.A. & U.K. has more impact on the world's educational system. Historically, Indian education has been elitist. Traditional Hindu education was tailored to the needs of Brahmin boys who are taught to read and write by a Brahmin teacher. Under British rule from the 1700 to until 1947, India's education policies reinforced the pre-existing elitist tendencies, typing entrance and advancement in government service to academic education. U.S.A. is a new country of the new world. But it is the oldest democratic form of government. Most of the people migrate in this country from Europe. Europeans started schools on the basis of European culture and literature. The language was English, yet different cultures, traditions and customs influence the education in America. In the middle of 19th century, due to political and industrial education began to be included in the curriculum. Education was made free and compulsory for boys and girls up to 16 years of age.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to do the comparative study between structure of education system of India and U.S.A at Secondary Level.

Review of Literature

The origin of secondary education in India with the efforts of **Christian Missionaries**. They established private instructions in Bengal during the later part of 18th and beginning of 19th century with the main purpose of spreading English education, European Culture and Christian faith amongst the natives.

The Secondary stage consists of grade 9-12 (ages 14-17). India has more than one hundred thousand secondary and senior secondary schools serving 30 million students. Historically, Secondary Education in India starts with **charter act of 1813**. Putting the responsibility of education on East India Company. Macaulay's Minute (1835) recommended European literature and Science. The Wood's Dispatch (1854) recommended English as the medium of instruction.

The number of secondary or High schools/ Intermediate colleges increased as a result of the **Calcutta university** commission. Sergeant Report (1944) also helped in growth of Secondary Education.

Secondary Education commission (1952-53) under **Dr. Laxman Mudaliar** recommended new pattern 10+2+3 and then Kothari commission (1964-66), National Policy on Education NPE (1986) has provide new direction for Secondary education.

Main Text

Public schools were more popular and effective than private education in the schools. Today, students get education and are trained according to his interest, aptitude, ability & needs in U.S.A.

India & U.S.A. both countries have great contribution in educational field. With the introduction of new scientific & technological outlook students are getting adequate knowledge in all fields. Young minds are curious and inquisitive about all things. The aim of education in India and USA is not only to make their children more knowledgeable and confident enough but also to bring awareness of a sort which would be their life long companion and help them grow as a person.

The secondary educational pattern of world is always influenced by USA e.g. the diversification of courses; curriculum reform and improvements in methods of teaching are initiated with help of USA.

Thus, the comparative study of education system of India and USA with special reference to structure in our secondary education. The study must fulfill the requirements of youth in modern Indian context and must lead to steps of success.

Secondary Education in India

Secondary education is the stage of education after Primary stage and before the higher stage. It may be called the final stage of compulsory education. The main aim of secondary education is to prepare person for higher education or vocational education. So a person may be trained directly to a profession.

Structure of Secondary Education

In India, Secondary Education has taken different meaning. The NCERT 'National Curriculum framework for school Education' (2000) used two terms:
Secondary stage (class 9th and 10th)
Higher Secondary stage (class 11th and 12th)

The National Policy on Education (1986) and revised policy in 1992 has explained the structure of National system of Education as:
"The National system of Education envisages a common education structure." The 10+2+3 pattern of education has now been accepted in all parts of the country.

Types of Schools

In India, the school is mainly divided into three parts.

1. Government School

According to current estimate 80% of all school is government school making the government the major provider of education. Education in government school to be free for grades a and all that the majority of enrollments are in private schools whose fees varies considerably. These are financed by the state government and their number is increasing by the year with a different pattern. The students whose parents are government servants and are transferred at regular intervals. There is regular growth of institutions like – Sainik schools, Kendriya Vidyalayas and Navodaya Vidyalayas in the government sector.

2. Private Schools

Private Schools often provide superior results at multiple of the unit cost of governmental Schools. In these schools, most of the teachers are female. And teacher student ratio is (1:37). These schools are managed by local bodies or religious institutions. Besides, they get grant-in-aid, from their state govt. only very few people gain education from these Schools.

3. Public Schools

In India and Sri Lanka due to British influence, a public school implies to a non-governmental historically elite educational institutions, often modeled on British public schools. There are privately owned and managed schools, many of whom have the appellation Public attached to them, e.g. the Delhi Public Schools, National Public Schools or Frank Anthony Public Schools. The medium of education is English but Hindi and/or the state's official language is also taught as a compulsory subject. Because of poor quality of public education 27% of Indian children are privately educated.

The following types of secondary schools are generally found in Indian:

Intermediate Colleges.
High School and Junior High Schools.
Higher Secondary Schools.
Multi-Purposes Schools.
Special Schools.

4. Intermediate Colleges

According to this system classes VI, VII and VIII are grouped under lower secondary classes IX and X are termed as "High School" and classes 11th and 12th are known as "Higher Secondary".

5. High School and Junior high School

In these schools classes 6th, 7th and 8th are grouped under "Junior High School" and classes 9th and 10th are known: High School. The Junior High School was formerly known as Middle School.

6. Higher Secondary School

According to the recommendations of Mudaliar commission and Kothari commission has advised the states to run three year higher secondary schools and three year degree courses. But State governments are not taking interest in opening of Higher Secondary Schools, because they cannot appoint the necessary number of teachers. The three year

degree courses have been organized at places where three years secondary courses are in operation.

7. Multipurpose Schools

Mudaliar Commission recommended the opening of multi purpose schools for giving a more meaningful vocational and pragmatic base to education at the secondary stage. This system is regarded as very expensive, because a multi-purpose school requires a special school building, various types of tools, implements, laboratories, land for framing workshop regarding rooms and other reasonable facilities. Arranging format least two or more types of vocations in the schools becomes all the more expensive.

Multi purpose schools may be opened as modals in government institutions only. The private institutions cannot run such schools for obvious reasons.

8. Special schools

During fifth five year Plan only about 500 Secondary schools teaching special courses in an agriculture, cottage, industries, gardening, could be organized in the country. Now more attention is needed towards this development during the sixth five year plan period.

Conclusion

The present investigator while engaged in the present work chanced upon several significant issues which require further better understanding on the basis of experience gained by the investigator the following suggestions are as under:

1. A comparative study of vocational education at the secondary level in USA and India.
2. A study of teacher education programmed in America.
3. A study of curriculum organization in the different states of India.
4. A comparative study of evaluation system on India and USA.
5. American Influence on Indian educational system after independence.
6. A study of impact of UK and USA on Indian education system.

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